
About the motivation: as an anti-corruption factor

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Abstract

The aim of the research, which is the basis of the article and which continues the overall lasting interests of the author on the topic, is to show and prove the relationship between motivation – an essential function of government, with corruption as a negative social phenomenon with particularly serious consequences for society. Some of the main elements of the motivation of employees and corruption respectively are briefly considered, and a relation is made between them regarding the influence of motivation as an anti-corruption factor. The scientific methods used in the research are mainly qualitative empirical-theoretical. The results of a study on the topic are cited. The originality of the results is contained in the formulated thesis that “Employee motivation is definitely an anti-corruption factor!”, based on which synthesized consequences (such as sub-theses) and relevant conclusions, with its scientific and practical value.

Key words: Motivation, corruption, anti-corruption, research.

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Introduction

Exploring management as a process that drives the development of humanity, in all its manifestations, phases, elements and other details, and in particular the strategic one, the focus of my scientific and scientific-practical interest is focused on the power that drives individuals (appearing both as subjects and as objects) to act. From the General Theory of management, we know that its main functions, according to the classification of the French theorist of management Henri Fayol (29.07.1841-19.11.1925), author of a Doctrine of the functioning of the administration, they are: anticipation, organization, leadership, coordination and control. To a large extent, they remain in this most general form to this day, when they are considered to be planning, organizing, coordinating, motivating and controlling. The difference is that the “motivation” function is included, which is already a mandatory part of the management whose object is the people.

Material and methods

The purpose of this article is to present to the scientific community my point of view on the relationship between motivation and corruption, as I have made a brief introductory review of both concepts, in addition to the results of my study 15 years ago, part of which is a survey of employees of the state administration. Based on the results, as well as analyzing the additional factors, conclusions are made and a main thesis is formulated, with several consequences as sub-theses. The methods used in the research, subject of the article, are empirical-theoretical, mostly qualitative, such as: analysis, observation, comparison, survey/interviews, synthesis, updating, expert evaluation and relevant verification.

Results and Discussion

The motivation of human resources (called in different ways: staff, personnel, workforce, labor capacity, employees, workers, etc.) is one of the main functions of modern quality and effective management. Motivating human resources to increase their efficiency through the use of appropriate tools and techniques, the dynamics of motivational mechanisms and their management in all conditions, especially in a crisis, is a key issue and a serious task to solve, in very strong connection with other public processes and individual activities. This task is a serious challenge for various spheres of human existence, an important factor in increasing productivity and raising the rating of the organization, trying to find its place in the conditions in which it is forced to operate and exist (Alashki, 2010).

Especially in times of crisis, it is important to know and use the full range of motivational mechanisms to maintain the motivation, productivity and creativity of employees. Overwhelmed by the many problems, managers at different levels of the management chain often forget some basic rules, which are even more important to follow when looking beyond the crisis. One of them is that the motivation of employees is the inner motivation that makes them act in a certain way. With regard to the labor process, it is a choice of work behavior by employees, expressed through commitment to the goals of the organization and work activity. The main levers of motivation are stimuli (which are external factors) and motives (human internal goals). Motivation is the ability of each manager to find the specific motive (incentive) for each employee to fully invest effort and skills in the work process. This is a set of measures that affect and initiate the individual and group behavior of workers in this labor process, their activity and willingness to work effectively (Maslow, 1943).

The other concept that is in the focus of this presentation, apart from motivation, is corruption. It is a social phenomenon known since ancient times, but in modern times with increasing influence on social processes (although if the “time machine” could take us back centuries, we would probably witness no less than form and manifestation of its influence). Corruption is the subject of serious public debate, commented on and studied in connection with its influence in various (and increasingly) public spheres and forms of manifestation. However, although it sounds somewhat paradoxical, there is still a lack of a clear and well-structured view of society, even in very economically and socially developed countries, of its nature and characteristics. There is still no unified and generally accepted understanding of what corruption is in the public consciousness, it is often thought of as something that is taken for granted and does not need special wording. The problem is complicated by the fact that there is no clear and unambiguous legal definition of the term “corruption”, although it is used as a legal and official term in a number of formalized publicly widely used documents, including regulations. However, different content and context are used in it. This ambiguity is complemented by the vague use of the term in the fields of political science, economics, ethics, morality, journalistic practice, etc. Therefore, it is necessary to define in more detail and precisely the possible interpretations (analytical, legal, international, private, public, daily, etc.) and to introduce a certain “uniformity” in the understanding and understanding of the term “corruption”. In this regard, I will introduce some basic characteristics that will mark the concept (Silagi, 1992a):

The realization of corruption presupposes the existence of four necessary elements:

1. Employee/ employees in a certain sector (generally public).
2. The so-called “Discretionary power” – the ability to make independent decisions.
3. Abuse of public authority by the employee/employees.
4. Deriving personal (or group) benefit.

The general rule is that corruption thrives when institutions are weak and market principles in the economy are limited. It manifests itself where the selfish interest finds favorable opportunities and prerequisites for realization. Corruption is a very serious field for studying, researching, analyzing and drawing conclusions, leading to a deeper understanding of the phenomenon, in order to counter it more effectively.

The connection between the motivation of the employee in the performance of his official duties and corruption is interesting. Is his motivation sufficient, to what extent and to what extent,

which form of its manifestation is the strongest, etc. so that it can be a factor in its counteraction – stopping (or to some extent limiting, influencing in a certain way) the submission to corruption pressure?

Motivation is the driving force behind all the actions of the individual. It includes targeted behavior and requires a direct and timely link between targeted action and results achieved. The end result is generally subjective and of psychological value. In psychology, motivation refers to the beginning, direction, intensity and consistency of behavior, desire and willingness to do something. Motivation is a temporary and dynamic state that should not be confused with individual traits of a person's character or emotional states. It is the force that makes people act, treat someone or something in different situations and circumstances in a way they choose. In everyday speech, motivation is used in three different senses (Silagi, 1992b):

- As the goals and reasons why, people make their choice of behavior and determine their actions. Usually, what makes people do something is the fulfillment of the set task or the desire to achieve the chosen goals, to occupy a higher social status, to achieve the desired power and influence, to have friendship, the necessary funds and more.

- As a thought process on the basis of which people form their behavior to achieve their goals. For example, people want to be friends with someone, to develop some of their expectations, to hope for influence, to decide how to act, and so on.

- As a social process through which some individuals can change the behavior of others. For example, friendship could be used to suggest other influences.

Motivation is driven by emotion (wikipedia.org, 2021). The word “emotion” itself has the same root as the word “motion”. When you want to challenge people to an action, you have to focus on their emotions. The act of motivation is an act of emotion. In any managerial endeavor, it should be ensured that people have a strong emotional commitment to realize it.

The main signs and factors of motivation are: perspective; development; recognition; salary; team; working conditions, and some of the motivating factors are: level and dynamics of wages; recognition of achievements in work; participation of employees in the distribution of profits; presentation of specific and higher requirements to the staff, etc. The main methods of motivation through remuneration are: money, approval, remuneration through free time, mutual understanding and expression of interest in the employee, promotion in the service hierarchy, providing opportunities for independence and liked work, awards, etc.

Corruption (Latin: *corrumpo* – spoil, corrupt, bribe) in the most general sense it is the abuse of public service (public position) for personal gain or, in particular, the conduct of officials by which they or their relatives benefit illegally and unlawfully by abusing the power entrusted to them. All forms of government are vulnerable to corruption, ranging significantly from small-scale use of influence to service to institutionalized bribery and beyond. The end point of corruption is kleptocracy, in which even external claims to integrity are abandoned.

Regarding the relationship between motivation and corruption towards public administration employees, years ago I conducted a study to understand the two subject concepts (such as phenomena and causation) in one of the main departments, part of the National Security Protection System. The following questions were asked in a survey of the interviewed employees (Alashki, 2010):

1. Do you think that motivation (whatever you mean by it) plays a crucial role for you in the performance of your official duties?

2. Are you motivated enough to invest 100% in your work?

3. What is your motivation (with more than one answer)?

4. For you, is motivation driven by emotion?

5. Do you need to be constantly motivated?

6. Assess motivational factors, according to the influence on you.

7. Can motivation be defined as an anti-corruption factor?

8. Do you think that the management of the administrative structure in which you work is aware of the impact of motivation on staff and work purposefully for its growth?

9. How much do you think your salary should be enough to not succumb to corruption pressure?

10. Would you succumb (tempted) to corruption pressure with a very profitable offer (financial, material, benefits, etc.)?

11. Do you think that Bulgarian People's psychology presupposes corruption?

12. Is the Bulgarian citizen corrupt?

In summarizing the results and analyzing the answers, conclusions and results were synthesized, on the basis of which the following **main thesis was formulated: "Employee motivation is definitely an anti-corruption factor!"**. This thesis has the following 4 consequences (as sub-theses):

A. Employee motivation is a powerful tool for influencing corruption.

B. Motivation is the strongest tool for the development and improvement of which it is possible to work purposefully, and this work is likely to lead to results.

C. Corruption is a social phenomenon that is a scourge of society and its degree depends (as a function) on the development of society itself.

D. Both the motivation and the degree of counteraction against corruption are directly dependent (in direct function) on the degree of development of society, the main element of which is the so-called "People's psychology" (used in terms of mentality and national characteristics) of its citizens.

From the main thesis and its sub-theses, it follows:

Conclusion 1. Motivation must be researched, studied, known and applied.

To this end, it is necessary to work in general coordination of governmental and non-governmental agencies and organizations, legislatures, research units and educational institutions of all degrees, and heads of business units (companies, administrative structures, etc.) who have delegated management rights. of human resources. Efforts are also needed on the part of the employees themselves to have the appropriate will and desire to be motivated.

Conclusion 2. The process should be continuous, with the development and modernization of the tools, methods and tools used.

To this end, efforts are needed on the part of the above-mentioned factors (subjects of the process) at very different levels, expressed in the provision of the necessary resources for its implementation.

Conclusion 3. Corruption should not be used; it should be a "thorn in the eye" of every element of society that needs to be eliminated by all means.

To this end, and because corruption is a function of society, it must be constantly evolving, which requires measures by both responsible state actors and the legislature, and last but not least, by the person who is the object and subject of the phenomenon.

Conclusion 4. The work regarding the national psychological peculiarities (mentality) should be in the focus of the activities mentioned above.

For this purpose, the strengths of the national self-confidence and the unique opportunity provided by our country's membership in the European Union and its accession to the nations, i.e. the development of a European nation while preserving the best national characteristics, should be used.

Conclusions

In conclusion, it can be stated that the study discussed above considers one of the most powerful "levers" to fight corruption as a social phenomenon. It attempts to formulate the thesis that motivation plays an important role as an anti-corruption factor, in relation to the formulated consequences of the thesis, conclusions and directions for action to implement successful counteraction. However, corruption cannot be eradicated or eliminated, for example, by a single law or the goodwill of a government, only by using a form of counteraction, even if it is extremely effective and efficient. A set of actions is needed, aimed directly (direct) and indirectly (indirect) against the vicious phenomenon.

An appropriate and meaningfully consistent ending would be the words of Seneca (*Latin: Lucius Annaeus Seneca is a Roman philosopher and writer, one of the most prominent Roman thinkers, a representative of late Stoicism*) who said that “there is no place for drug where what was considered a vice becomes a custom”. Paraphrasing through the prism of what has been said so far about the "motivation" factor and the phenomenon of “corruption” and the influence of one on the other for the working (serving) person, Seneca would sound like this: use the drug “mottivato” to cure our disease “Corrumpto”, while this phenomenon is still classified as a disease (albeit severe, chronic, even inherited), before it is a common incurable disease that, yes – can be lived with, but difficult, limited, dishonestly and to the detriment of others. The terms are deliberately written in Latin, because diseases (and some drugs) traditionally have Latin names.

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